

LEARNING GAP ASSESSMENT IN FILIPINO SA PILING LARANGAN (TECH-VOC)

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Article history:	Abstract:
Received: January 10 th 2024 Accepted: March 6 th 2024	This study aimed to determine the learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc) for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023. A quantitative quasi-experimental research using a pretest-posttest design was employed in this study. It was conducted to the 33 Grade 12 TVL students of St. Paul University Surigao during the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023. A validated test was used in conducting the pre-test and post-test in assessing the learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). Five competencies that were least mastered showed significant progress and improvement. However, despite the interventions implemented, the learning gap resulted in only average mastery. As to their performance in terms of scores for pre-test most of the students belong to the average. After the intervention given, most of the students belong to the good level during the post-test. Furthermore, it showed that there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results after implementing an intervention. It is recommended that Paulinian Filipino teachers may reassess the areas that require additional attention in instructional delivery to address the persistent learning gap and achieve mastery, despite the interventions that were implemented.

Keywords: Learning gaps, Learning gap assessment, Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)

1. INTRODUCTION

As the education system transitions back to in-person classes after the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a need to assess the learning gaps and evaluate the impact of the pandemic on teaching Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). The pandemic disruption in education has been projected to result in a significant learning loss, which may be particularly profound for students from disadvantaged backgrounds, leading to widening opportunity gaps (Namkung, et.al., 2022). The prolonged period of remote learning may have resulted in learning gaps and hindered students' language proficiency in Filipino sa Piling Larangan. As mentioned by Collins (2021) COVID-19 pandemic had created significant learning gaps for students nationwide; youth impacted by systemic inequities were disproportionately affected, exacerbating disparities within our education systems. Educators are now challenged to meet students where they are while simultaneously addressing the learning gap created by the pandemic (Gaddi et al., 2024).

The disruption caused by the pandemic calls for a comprehensive learning gap assessment in Filipino sa Piling Larangan to identify the specific areas where Tech-Voc students may have experienced challenges in language proficiency (Gaddi, 2024). Diagnostic test is one of the educational assessments' teachers used to determine the learning gaps. Educational assessment is a process for obtaining information that can be used for making decisions about students; teachers, curricula, programs, and schools; funding; and other aspects of educational policy (NAE, 2021). By conducting a post-pandemic diagnostic test, educational stakeholders can gain insights into the areas that require improvement and develop appropriate measures to enhance language instruction. This may include implementing targeted interventions, providing additional support for students who experienced learning gaps, and refining the curriculum to address the language competencies gap.

The assessment will also evaluate the effectiveness of strategies implemented during the pandemic to address language learning in the Tech-Voc sector. As cited from the study of Gaddi et al. (2024), this assessment aims to uncover specific topics or concepts where students may struggle, providing educators with critical insights to design targeted interventions and instructional strategies that effectively address these gaps.

Furthermore, the Surigao del Norte encountered an additional obstacle in the form of Typhoon Odette, which caused significant damage to Surigao City, including schools, and resulted in a prolonged electricity outage lasting nearly three months (Languing et al., 2023). This super typhoon further disrupted education in the place as there was no access to wifi or stable internet connections. As a result, St. Paul University Surigao had to adapt its approach from online classes to distributing printed modules to students and assessing their learning based on the materials provided (Gaddi et al., 2024).

With these, the researchers prompted to conduct this study about the learning gap assessment in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). Through this study, it addressed the challenges and identify the areas of improvement where educators can help students regain and enhance their language competencies, ensuring their preparedness for success in their vocational fields.

Overall, this research study contributes to the ongoing efforts to recover from the impact of the pandemic and improve language instruction in the Tech-Voc sector. It emphasizes the importance of assessing and addressing the learning gaps to provide Tech-Voc students with the necessary language skills to thrive in their vocational fields.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc) for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the identified learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)?
2. What is the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)?
4. What interventions may be proposed?

2. METHODS

A quantitative quasi-experimental research using a pretest-posttest design was employed in this study. In this design, the dependent variable is measured once before the treatment is implemented and once after it is implemented (Serato et al., 2024). This study was conducted to the 33 Grade 12 TVL students of St. Paul University Surigao during the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023. A validated test was used in conducting the pre-test and post-test in assessing the learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). The participants were given an intervention, especially on the identified least learned competencies, before they took the post test. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution and paired t-test were used in analyzing the data gathered.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part presents the result and discussion of the data. The data presented follows the order of the problems cited in the problem statement.

Identified learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)

Table 1 presents the identified learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc) for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Table 1. *Identified learning gaps in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)*

Learning Competencies	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	%	Interpretation	%	Interpretation
<i>The learner...</i>				
Nabibigyang-kahulugan ang teknikal at bokasyunal na sulatin CS_FTV11/12PB-0a-c-105	30.30%	Low Mastery	64.65%	Average Mastery
EC: Nakikilala ang iba't ibang teknikal-bokasyunal na sulatin ayon sa: Layunin, Gamit, Katangian, Anyo & Target na gagamit CS_FTV11/12PT-0a-c-93	29.29%	Low Mastery	58.59%	Average Mastery
Pre-requisites: Naiisa-isa ang mga hakbang sa pagbuo ng isang makabuluhang pananaliksik F11PU – Iig	32.32%	Low Mastery	40.40%	Average Mastery

Learning Competencies	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	%	Interpretation	%	Interpretation
<i>The learner...</i>				
Naiisa-isa ang mga paraan at tamang proseso ng pagsulat ng isang pananaliksik sa Filipino batay sa layunin, gamit, metodo, at etika ng pananaliksik F11PU – IVef – 91	31.31%	Low Mastery	51.52%	Average Mastery

As presented in the table, the competency with *Low Mastery* in the pre-test were considered as the learning gaps that were addressed during the quarter. The competency *Nabibigyang-kahulugan ang teknikal at bokasyunal na sulatin CS_FTV11/12PB-0a-c-105, Natutukoy ang paksang tinalakay sa iba't ibang tekstong binasa F11PB – IIIa – 98, Nakikilala ang iba't ibang teknikal-bokasyunal na sulatin ayon sa: Layunin, Gamit, Katangian, Anyo & Target na gagamit CS_FTV11/12PT-0a-c-93, Naiisa-isa ang mga hakbang sa pagbuo ng isang makabuluhang pananaliksik F11PU – IIg – 88, Naiisa-isa ang mga paraan at tamang proseso ng pagsulat ng isang pananaliksik sa Filipino batay sa layunin, gamit, metodo, at etika ng pananaliksik F11PU – IVef – 91* got a *low mastery* description with 30.30%, 27.27%, 29.29%, 32.32%, 31.31% mastery level, respectively.

Pre- and post-test performance of the learners

Table 2 presents the Pre- and Post-test performance of the learners in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc) for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Table 2. *Pre- and post-test of the Learners for Quarter 1 in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)*

Scores	f (n=33)	%
Pre-Test		
Poor	5	15.15
Average	14	42.42
Good	13	39.39
Excellent	1	3.03
Post-Test		
Average	11	33.33
Good	17	51.52
Excellent	5	15.15

The distribution of scores for the pre-test, which was completed by 33 students in total (n=33), is as follows:

- Poor: 5 students—or 15.15 percent of the total—received scores in this category.
- 14 students, or 42.42% of the total, received scores in this range, which is the average.
- Good: 13 students—or 39.39% of the group—received scores in this range.
- Excellent: Only 1 learner, or 3.03% of all students, received a score in this range.

Following were the changes to the score distribution in the post-test:

- 11 students, or 33.33% of the total, received scores in this range, which is the average.
- Good: 17 students—or 51.52% of the group—received scores in this range.
- Excellent: 5 students, or 15.15 percent of the total, received scores in this category.

From the pre-test to the post-test, there seems to have been a decline in both the number and percentage of students scoring in the "Average" level. On the other hand, there was a rise in the quantity and proportion of students receiving "Good" ratings. Additionally, from 1 to 5, there were somewhat more students who scored in the "Excellent" range. It's important to note that it is challenging to provide a thorough interpretation of what these results signify in terms of the learners' success in the subject without more context or information about the scoring criteria or the importance of these scores.

Table 3. *Significant difference in the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc)*

Scores	t	df	p-value	Decision
Pre-Test – Post-Test	-3.04	64	0.0034	Reject H ₀

The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results after implementing an intervention, particularly for students with low mastery levels ($p = 0.0034$), at a significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the intervention strategies employed by the teacher, such as incorporating the least mastered competencies as a review, facilitating collaborative tasks to address those competencies, and conducting assessments to monitor improvement, have a significant impact on mastering the competencies in the First Quarter of Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). According to Sewell (2021), targeted interventions are crucial for addressing the learning gaps caused by the pandemic as students who have fallen behind often hesitate to participate in class. Offering personalized instruction through differentiated or individualized help from educators is the most effective way to address and eliminate these learning gaps (Gaddi, 2024).

Table 4. *Intervention given on the least mastered Competencies*

Least Mastered Competencies	Interventions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nabibigyang-kahulugan ang teknikal at bokasyunal na sulatin CS_FTV11/12PB-0a-c-105 	Employed various instructional strategies, such as explicit teaching of technical and vocational writing principles, modeling and guided practice.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-requisite: Natutukoy ang paksa ng tinalakay sa iba't ibang tekstong binasa F11PB – IIIa – 98 	Conducted educational games to help the learners become familiarized with the concepts needed to master this least mastered competency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EC: Nakikilala ang iba't ibang teknikal-bokasyunal na sulatin ayon sa: Layunin, Gamit, Katangian, Anyo & Target na gagamit CS_FTV11/12PT-0a-c-93 	Engaged in authentic writing tasks related to their chosen technical or vocational field. These tasks may include writing reports, instructions, procedures, and other relevant documents commonly encountered in real-world vocational settings.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-requisites: Naiisa-isa ang mga hakbang sa pagbuo ng isang makabuluhang pananaliksik F11PU – IIg – 88 	Conducted collaborative tasks addressing this least-mastered competency.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Naiisa-isa ang mga paraan at tamang proseso ng pagsulat ng isang pananaliksik sa Filipino batay sa layunin, gamit, metodo, at etika ng pananaliksik F11PU – IVef – 91 	Integrated the technology tools and resources in working this least mastered competency.

The data above shows the intervention given by the teacher to address the least mastered competencies. It can be observed that there are five least mastered competencies and these competencies were given interventions to address the learning gap. With the help of various strategies and techniques in education, the learning gap were addressed. However, only average mastery was the result of the post-test.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that there were varying levels of mastery and learning gaps observed during the first quarter of Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). Five competencies that were least mastered showed significant progress and improvement. However, despite the interventions implemented, the learning gap resulted in only average mastery. This suggests that additional attention and further interventions may be necessary to achieve mastery in those areas. The study provides valuable insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers, offering guidance in designing interventions and instructional practices that specifically address the identified learning gaps. By doing so, it aims to enhance student learning outcomes and improve the overall quality of education at St. Paul University Surigao, particularly in the field of Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc).

5. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and the significance of this study, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Paulinian Filipino teachers may reassess the areas that require additional attention in instructional delivery to address the persistent learning gap and achieve mastery, despite the interventions that were implemented.
2. Interventions may continue such as providing supplementary worksheets, facilitating collaborative tasks, and conducting ongoing assessments to track students' progress. These interventions should be tailored to accommodate students' individual learning styles and promote improvement in their mastery level.
3. Future research endeavors could explore the learning gap assessment in Filipino subjects across different grade levels, expanding the scope of investigation to gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities for improvement in Filipino language education.

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